

References of the “Memoria” document written by Swen Brands, Instituto de Física de Cantabria (CSIC-UC), ORCID 0000-0002-3254-0277 to apply for a Ramón y Cajal 2025 contract

- Anstey, James A., Isla R. Simpson, Jadwiga H. Richter, Hiroaki Naoe, Masakazu Taguchi, Federico Serva, Lesley J. Gray, Neal Butchart, Kevin Hamilton, Scott Osprey, Omar Bellprat, Peter Braesicke, Andrew C. Bushell, Chiara Cagnazzo, Chih-Chieh Chen, Hye-Yeong Chun, Rolando R. Garcia, Laura Holt, Yoshio Kawatani, Tobias Kerzenmacher, Young-Ha Kim, Francois Lott, Charles McLandress, John Scinocca, Timothy N. Stockdale, Stefan Versick, Shingo Watanabe, Kohei Yoshida, and Seiji Yukimoto. 2022. “Teleconnections of the Quasi-Biennial Oscillation in a Multi-Model Ensemble of QBO-Resolving Models.” *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 148 (744): 1568–92. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4048>.
- Barnston, Anthony G., and Robert E. Livezey. 1987. “Classification, Seasonality and Persistence of Low-Frequency Atmospheric Circulation Patterns.” *Monthly Weather Review*. *Monthly Weather Review* 115 (6): 1083–126. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1987\)115%253C1083:CSAPOL%253E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1987)115%253C1083:CSAPOL%253E2.0.CO;2).
- Beguiría, Santiago, Sergio M. Vicente-Serrano, José Manuel Gutiérrez-Llorente, Swen Brands, Marcos Gil-Guallar, Alejandro Royo-Aranda, María Del Mar Rondón-Velasco, Antonio Torralba-Gallego, Yolanda Luna, and Ana Morata. 2026. “A Hierarchical Bayesian Spatio-Temporal Model for Estimating Solar Radiation from Sunshine Duration Records.” *Renewable Energy* 256 (January): 123943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123943>.
- Belleflamme, Alexandre, Xavier Fettweis, Charlotte Lang, and Michel Erpicum. 2013. “Current and Future Atmospheric Circulation at 500 hPa over Greenland Simulated by the CMIP3 and CMIP5 Global Models.” *Climate Dynamics* 41 (7): 2061–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-012-1538-2>.
- Boer, George J., Douglas M. Smith, Christophe Cassou, Francisco Doblado-Reyes, Gokhan Danabasoglu, Ben Kirtman, Yochanan Kushnir, Masahide Kimoto, Gerald A. Meehl, and Rym Msadek. 2016. “The Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP) Contribution to CMIP6.” *Geoscientific Model Development* 9 (10): 3751–77. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3751-2016>.
- Brands, S. 2013. “Skillful Seasonal Predictions of Boreal Winter Accumulated Heating Degree-Days and Relevance for the Weather Derivative Market.” *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology* 52 (6): 1297–302. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-12-0303.1>.
- Brands, S., J. M. Gutiérrez, S. Herrera, and A. S. Cofiño. 2012a. “On the Use of Reanalysis Data for Downscaling.” *Journal of Climate*. *Journal of Climate* 25 (7): 2517–26. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-11-00251.1>.
- Brands, S., J. M. Gutiérrez, and D. San-Martín. 2017. “Twentieth-Century Atmospheric River Activity along the West Coasts of Europe and North America: Algorithm Formulation, Reanalysis Uncertainty and Links to Atmospheric Circulation Patterns.” *Climate Dynamics* 48 (9): 2771–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-016-3095-6>.

- Brands, S., S. Herrera, J. Fernández, and J. M. Gutiérrez. 2013. "How Well Do CMIP5 Earth System Models Simulate Present Climate Conditions in Europe and Africa?" *Climate Dynamics* 41 (3): 803–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-013-1742-8>.
- Brands, S., S. Herrera, and J.M. Gutiérrez. 2014. "Is Eurasian Snow Cover in October a Reliable Statistical Predictor for the Wintertime Climate on the Iberian Peninsula?" *International Journal of Climatology* 34 (5): 1615–27. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.3788>.
- Brands, S., S. Herrera, D. San-Martín, and J. M. Gutiérrez. 2011a. "Validation of the ENSEMBLES Global Climate models over Southwestern Europe Using Probability Density Functions, from a Downscaling Perspective." *Climate Research* 48 (2–3): 145–61. <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr00995>.
- Brands, S., J. J. Taboada, A. S. Cofiño, T. Sauter, and C. Schneider. 2011b. "Statistical Downscaling of Daily Temperatures in the NW Iberian Peninsula from Global Climate Models: Validation and Future Scenarios." *Climate Research* 48 (2–3): 163–76. <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr00906>.
- Brands, S., R. Manzananas, J. M. Gutiérrez, and J. Cohen. 2012b. "Seasonal Predictability of Wintertime Precipitation in Europe Using the Snow Advance Index." *Journal of Climate*. *Journal of Climate* 25 (12): 4023–28. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00083.1>.
- Brands, Swen. 2014. "Predicting Average Wintertime Wind and Wave Conditions in the North Atlantic Sector from Eurasian Snow Cover in October." *Environmental Research Letters* 9 (4): 045006. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/9/4/045006>.
- Brands, Swen. 2017a. *Oceanic and Atmospheric Precursors of Atmospheric River Activity along the West Coasts of Europe and Western North America*. September 22. <https://repositorio.unican.es/xmlui/handle/10902/12384>.
- Brands, Swen. 2017b. "Which ENSO Teleconnections Are Robust to Internal Atmospheric Variability?" *Geophysical Research Letters* 44 (3): 1483–93. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL071529>.
- Brands, Swen, J. Gutiérrez, and Daniel San-Martin. 2017. "Six-Hourly Atmospheric River Presence-Absence Time Series for Europe (1900-2014)." September 28. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14711.32160>.
- Brands, Swen. 2018. *Proxeccións Climatolóxicas para o Monumento Natural da Serra de Pena Corneira*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781713>.
- Brands, Swen, Guillermo Fernández-García, Marta García Vivanco, Marcos Tesouro Montecelo, Nuria Gallego Fernández, Anthony David Saunders Estévez, Pablo Enrique Carracedo García, Anabela Neto Venâncio, Pedro Melo Da Costa, Paula Costa Tomé, Cristina Otero, María Luz Macho, and Juan Taboada. 2020. "An Exploratory Performance Assessment of the CHIMERE Model (Version 2017r4) for the Northwestern Iberian Peninsula and the Summer Season." *Geoscientific Model Development* 13 (9): 3947–73. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-3947-2020>.
- Brands, Swen. 2022a. "A Circulation-Based Performance Atlas of the CMIP5 and 6 Models for Regional Climate Studies in the Northern Hemisphere Mid-to-High Latitudes." *Geoscientific Model Development* 15 (4): 1375–411. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-1375-2022>.

- Brands, Swen. 2022b. "Common Error Patterns in the Regional Atmospheric Circulation Simulated by the CMIP Multi-Model Ensemble." *Geophysical Research Letters* 49 (23): e2022GL101446. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL101446>.
- Brands, Swen. 2023a. "20th Century Atmospheric River Archive for Western North America and Europe." June 6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8010793>.
- Brands, Swen. 2023b. "Northern Hemisphere Lamb Weather Types from Historical GCM Experiments and Various Reanalyses." Version v5. Zenodo, March 28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8113174>.
- Brands, S., J. A. Fernández-Granja, J. Bedia, A. Casanueva, and J. Fernández. 2023a. "A Global Climate Model Performance Atlas for the Southern Hemisphere Extratropics Based on Regional Atmospheric Circulation Patterns." *Geophysical Research Letters* 50 (10): e2023GL103531. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL103531>.
- Brands, Swen, Hiroaki Tatebe, Christopher Danek, Jesús Fernández, Neil C. Swart, Evgeny Volodin, YoungHo Kim, Mark Collier, Dave Bi, and Wu Tongwen. 2023b. *A Metadata Archive about Global Climate Model Complexity in CMIP*. V. v1.1. Zenodo, released March 10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7813495>.
- Brands, Swen, Juan Antonio Fernández-Granja, Joaquín Bedia, Ana Casanueva, and Jesús Fernández. 2023c. "Southern Hemisphere Lamb Weather Types from Historical GCM Experiments and Various Reanalyses." Version 2.0. Zenodo, April 27. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7872012>.
- Brands, Swen, Maialen Iturbide, Jaime Díez González-Pardo, Sixto Herrera, Joaquín Bedia, Rodrigo Manzananas, Esteban Rodríguez-Guisado, Santiago Beguería, Sergio M. Vicente-Serrano, and José Manuel Gutiérrez. 2025a. "Seasonal Drought Predictions in the Mediterranean Using the SPEI Index: Paving the Way for Their Operational Applicability in Climate Services." *Climate Services* 38 (April): 100555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2025.100555>.
- Brands, S., E. Cimadevilla, and J. Fernández. 2025b. "Predictability of Semiannual Atmospheric Circulation Type Frequencies in the Extratropics Using the EC-Earth3 Decadal Forecasting System." *Geophysical Research Letters* 52 (10): e2024GL114176. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL114176>.
- Brands, Swen, Jesús Fernández, Hugo Hidalgo, Rondrotiana Barimalala, Moetasim Ashfaq, Maria Laura Bettolli, Panos Hadjinicolaou, Silvina Solman, Douglas Maraun, Tereza Cavazos, Juan Antonio Fernandez De La Granja, Jose González-Abad, Julia Mindlin, Javier Soto-Navarro, Samuel Somot, Dominique Paquin, Hiroaki Kawase, Fatima Driouech, Andrew Orr, Lalu Das, Stefan Sobolowski, Rasmus E. Benestad, Thanh Ngo-Duc, Priscilla Mooney, Jason Evans, Erika Coppola, and José Manuel Gutiérrez. 2025c. *CORDEX Collection of Regional-Scale Climate Processes and Metrics for Climate Model Evaluation*. May 14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15348836>.
- Compo, G. P., J. S. Whitaker, P. D. Sardeshmukh, N. Matsui, R. J. Allan, X. Yin, B. E. Gleason, R. S. Vose, G. Rutledge, P. Bessemoulin, S. Brönnimann, M. Brunet, R. I. Crouthamel, A. N. Grant, P. Y. Groisman, P. D. Jones, M. C. Kruk, A. C. Kruger, G. J. Marshall, M. Maugeri, H. Y. Mok, Ø. Nordli, T. F. Ross, R. M. Trigo, X. L. Wang, S. D. Woodruff, and S. J. Worley. 2011. "The Twentieth Century Reanalysis Project."

Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society 137 (654): 1–28.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.776>.

- Deser, C., F. Lehner, K. B. Rodgers, T. Ault, T. L. Delworth, P. N. DiNezio, A. Fiore, C. Frankignoul, J. C. Fyfe, D. E. Horton, J. E. Kay, R. Knutti, N. S. Lovenduski, J. Marotzke, K. A. McKinnon, S. Minobe, J. Randerson, J. A. Screen, I. R. Simpson, and M. Ting. 2020. “Insights from Earth System Model Initial-Condition Large Ensembles and Future Prospects.” *Nature Climate Change* 10 (4): 4.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-0731-2>.
- Deser, Clara, Adam Phillips, Vincent Bourdette, and Haiyan Teng. 2012. “Uncertainty in Climate Change Projections: The Role of Internal Variability.” *Climate Dynamics* 38 (3): 527–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-010-0977-x>.
- Dunne, John P., Helene T. Hewitt, Julie M. Arblaster, Frédéric Bonou, Olivier Boucher, Tereza Cavazos, Beth Dingley, Paul J. Durack, Birgit Hassler, Martin Juckes, Tomoki Miyakawa, Matt Mizielinski, Vaishali Naik, Zebedee Nicholls, Eleanor O’Rourke, Robert Pincus, Benjamin M. Sanderson, Isla R. Simpson, and Karl E. Taylor. 2025. “An Evolving Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 7 (CMIP7) and Fast Track in Support of Future Climate Assessment.” *Geoscientific Model Development* 18 (19): 6671–700. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-18-6671-2025>.
- Eiras-Barca, Jorge, Swen Brands, and Gonzalo Miguez-Macho. 2016. “Seasonal Variations in North Atlantic Atmospheric River Activity and Associations with Anomalous Precipitation over the Iberian Atlantic Margin.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 121 (2): 931–48. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JD023379>.
- Fernández-Granja, Juan. A., Joaquín Bedia, Swen Brands, Ana Casanueva, and Jesús Fernández. 2025. “Global Extra-Tropical Circulation Database Based on the Jenkinson-Collision Classification Calculated with 6-Hourly Mean Sea-Level Pressure Fields from Various Reanalysis Datasets.” Zenodo, July 9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15847558>.
- Fernández-Granja, Juan A., Joaquín Bedia, Ana Casanueva, Swen Brands, and Jesús Fernández. 2024. “The Signature of the Main Modes of Climatic Variability as Revealed by the Jenkinson-Collision Classification over Europe.” *International Journal of Climatology* 44 (11): 4076–88. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.8569>.
- Fernández-Granja, Juan A., Swen Brands, Joaquín Bedia, Ana Casanueva, and Jesús Fernández. 2023. “Exploring the Limits of the Jenkinson–Collision Weather Types Classification Scheme: A Global Assessment Based on Various Reanalyses.” *Climate Dynamics* 61 (3): 1829–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-022-06658-7>.
- Geen, Ruth, Simona Bordoni, David S. Battisti, and Katrina Hui. 2020. “Monsoons, ITCZs, and the Concept of the Global Monsoon.” *Reviews of Geophysics* 58 (4): e2020RG000700. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020RG000700>.
- Gutiérrez, J. M., D. San-Martín, S. Brands, R. Manzananas, and S. Herrera. 2013. “Reassessing Statistical Downscaling Techniques for Their Robust Application under Climate Change Conditions.” *Journal of Climate*. *Journal of Climate* 26 (1): 171–88. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-11-00687.1>.
- Hassler, Birgit, Forrest M Hoffman, Rebecca Beadling, Ed Blockley, Bo Huang, Jiwoo Lee, Valerio Lembo, Jared Lewis, Jianhua Lu, Luke Madaus, Elizaveta Malinina, Brian Medeiros, Wilfried Pokam, Enrico Scoccimarro, and Ranjini Swaminathan. 2025.

“Systematic Benchmarking of Climate Models: Methodologies, Applications, and New Directions.” Preprint, March 14.
<https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.174196646.65056548/v1>.

Hausfather, Zeke, Kate Marvel, Gavin A. Schmidt, John W. Nielsen-Gammon, and Mark Zelinka. 2022. “Climate Simulations: Recognize the ‘Hot Model’ Problem.” *Nature* 605 (7908): 26–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01192-2>.

Hersbach, Hans, Bill Bell, Paul Berrisford, Shoji Hirahara, András Horányi, Joaquín Muñoz-Sabater, Julien Nicolas, Carole Peubey, Raluca Radu, Dinand Schepers, Adrian Simmons, Cornel Soci, Saleh Abdalla, Xavier Abellan, Gianpaolo Balsamo, Peter Bechtold, Gionata Biavati, Jean Bidlot, Massimo Bonavita, Giovanna De Chiara, Per Dahlgren, Dick Dee, Michail Diamantakis, Rossana Dragani, Johannes Flemming, Richard Forbes, Manuel Fuentes, Alan Geer, Leo Haimberger, Sean Healy, Robin J. Hogan, Elías Hólm, Marta Janisková, Sarah Keeley, Patrick Laloyaux, Philippe Lopez, Cristina Lupu, Gabor Radnoti, Patricia de Rosnay, Iryna Rozum, Freja Vamborg, Sebastien Villaume, and Jean-Noël Thépaut. 2020. “The ERA5 Global Reanalysis.” *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 146 (730): 1999–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>.

Hoffman, Forrest M., Birgit Hassler, Ranjini Swaminathan, Jared Lewis, Bouwe Andela, Nathaniel Collier, Dóra Hegedűs, Jiwoo Lee, Charlotte Pascoe, Mika Pflüger, Martina Stockhause, Paul Ullrich, Min Xu, Lisa Bock, Felicity Chun, Bettina K. Gier, Douglas I. Kelley, Axel Lauer, Julien Lenhardt, Manuel Schlund, Mohanan G. Sreeush, Katja Weigel, Ed Blockley, Rebecca Beadling, Romain Beucher, Demiso D. Dugassa, Valerio Lembo, Jianhua Lu, Swen Brands, Jerry Tjiputra, Elizaveta Malinina, Brian Medeiros, Enrico Scoccimarro, Jeremy Walton, Philip Kershaw, André L. Marquez, Malcolm J. Roberts, Eleanor O’Rourke, Elisabeth Dingley, Briony Turner, Helene Hewitt, and John P. Dunne. 2025. “Rapid Evaluation Framework for the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track.” *EGUsphere*, July 11, 1–57. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-2685>.

Inness, Antje, Melanie Ades, Anna Agustí-Panareda, Jérôme Barré, Anna Benedictow, Anne-Marlene Blechschmidt, Juan Jose Dominguez, Richard Engelen, Henk Eskes, Johannes Flemming, Vincent Huijnen, Luke Jones, Zak Kipling, Sebastien Massart, Mark Parrington, Vincent-Henri Peuch, Miha Razinger, Samuel Remy, Michael Schulz, and Martin Suttie. 2019. “The CAMS Reanalysis of Atmospheric Composition.” *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 19 (6): 3515–56. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-3515-2019>.

Iturbide, Maialen, Jesús Fernández, José M. Gutiérrez, Anna Pirani, David Huard, Alaa Al Khourdajie, Jorge Baño-Medina, Joaquin Bedia, Ana Casanueva, Ezequiel Cimadevilla, Antonio S. Cofiño, Matteo De Felice, Javier Diez-Sierra, Markel García-Díez, James Goldie, Dimitris A. Herrera, Sixto Herrera, Rodrigo Manzananas, Josipa Milovac, Aparna Radhakrishnan, Daniel San-Martín, Alessandro Spinuso, Kristen M. Thyng, Claire Trenham, and Özge Yelekçi. 2022. “Implementation of FAIR Principles in the IPCC: The WGI AR6 Atlas Repository.” *Scientific Data* 9 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01739-y>.

Ivanciu, Ioana, Katja Matthes, Sebastian Wahl, Jan Harlaß, and Arne Biastoch. 2021. “Effects of Prescribed CMIP6 Ozone on Simulating the Southern Hemisphere Atmospheric Circulation Response to Ozone Depletion.” *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 21 (8): 5777–806. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-5777-2021>.

- Rutz, Jonathan J., Christine A., Juan Manuel Lora, Ashley E. Payne, Bin Guan, Paul A. Ullrich, Travis Allen O'Brien, L. Ruby Leung, F. Martin Ralph, Michael F. Wehner, Swen Brands, Allison B. Marquardt Collow, Naomi Goldenson, Irina V. Gorodetskaya, Helen Griffith, Samson M. Hagos, Karthik Kashinath, Brian Kawzenuk, Harinarayan Krishnan, Vitaliy Kurlin, David Lavers, Gudrun Magnusdottir, Kelly Mahoney, Elizabeth McClenny, Grzegorz Muszynski, Phu Dinh Nguyen, Mr Prabhat, Yun Qian, Alexandre M. Ramos, Chandan Sarangi, Scott Sellars, T. Shulgina, Ricardo Tome, Duane Waliser, Daniel Walton, Gary Wick, Anna M. Wilson, and Maximiliano Viale. 2024. "Atmospheric River Tracking Method Intercomparison Project Tier 1 Source Data and Catalogues." NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research, November 7. <https://doi.org/10.5065/D62R3QFS>.
- Knutti, Reto, Reinhard Furrer, Claudia Tebaldi, Jan Cermak, and Gerald A. Meehl. 2010. "Challenges in Combining Projections from Multiple Climate Models." *Journal of Climate* 23 (10): 2739–58. <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JCLI3361.1>.
- Laloyaux, Patrick, Eric de Boisseson, Magdalena Balmaseda, Jean-Raymond Bidlot, Stefan Broennimann, Roberto Buizza, Per Dalhgren, Dick Dee, Leopold Haimberger, Hans Hersbach, Yuki Kosaka, Matthew Martin, Paul Poli, Nick Rayner, Elke Rustemeier, and Dinand Schepers. 2018. "CERA-20C: A Coupled Reanalysis of the Twentieth Century." *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 10 (5): 1172–95. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018MS001273>.
- Laprise, René, Mundakkara Ravi Varma, Bertrand Denis, Daniel Caya, and Isztar Zawadzki. 2000. "Predictability of a Nested Limited-Area Model." *Monthly Weather Review*. *Monthly Weather Review* 128 (12): 4149–54. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(2000\)129%253C4149:POANLA%253E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2000)129%253C4149:POANLA%253E2.0.CO;2).
- Lemus-Canovas, Marc, and Swen Brands. 2020. *Assessing Several Downscaling Methods for Daily Minimum and Maximum Temperature in a Mountainous Area. Are We Able to Statistically Simulate a Warmer Climate in the Pyrenees?* Nos. EGU2020-11389. EGU2020. Copernicus Meetings. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu2020-11389>.
- Lindzen, Richard S., and James R. Holton. 1968. "A Theory of the Quasi-Biennial Oscillation." *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 25 (6): 1095–107. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1968\)025%253C1095:ATOTQB%253E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1968)025%253C1095:ATOTQB%253E2.0.CO;2).
- Lorenzo, María N., Alexandre M. Ramos, and Swen Brands. 2016. "Present and Future Climate Conditions for Winegrowing in Spain." *Regional Environmental Change* 16 (3): 617–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0883-1>.
- Madden, Roland A., and Paul R. Julian. 1994. "Observations of the 40–50-Day Tropical Oscillation—A Review." *Monthly Weather Review*. *Monthly Weather Review* 122 (5): 814–37. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1994\)122%253C0814:OOTDTP%253E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1994)122%253C0814:OOTDTP%253E2.0.CO;2).
- Mahmood, Rashed, Markus G. Donat, Francisco J. Doblas-Reyes, and Etienne Tourigny. 2025. "A Perfect-Model Perspective on the Signal-to-Noise Paradox in Initialized Decadal Predictions." *Journal of Climate*. *Journal of Climate* 38 (12): 2841–51. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-24-0381.1>.
- Manzanas, R., S. Brands, D. San-Martín, A. Lucero, C. Limbo, and J. M. Gutiérrez. 2015. "Statistical Downscaling in the Tropics Can Be Sensitive to Reanalysis Choice: A

Case Study for Precipitation in the Philippines.” *Journal of Climate*. *Journal of Climate* 28 (10): 4171–84. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00331.1>.

- Maussion, F., W. Gurgiser, M. Großhauser, G. Kaser, and B. Marzeion. 2015. “ENSO Influence on Surface Energy and Mass Balance at Shallap Glacier, Cordillera Blanca, Peru.” *The Cryosphere* 9 (4): 1663–83. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-9-1663-2015>.
- Mishra, Aditya N., Douglas Maraun, Reinhard Schiemann, Kevin Hodges, Giuseppe Zappa, and Albert Ossó. 2025. “Long-Lasting Intense Cut-off Lows to Become More Frequent in the Northern Hemisphere.” *Communications Earth & Environment* 6 (1): 115. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02078-7>.
- O’Brien, Travis A., Ashley E. Payne, Christine A. Shields, Jonathan Rutz, Swen Brands, Christopher Castellano, Jiayi Chen, William Cleveland, Michael J. DeFlorio, Naomi Goldenson, Irina V. Gorodetskaya, Héctor Inda Díaz, Karthik Kashinath, Brian Kawzenuk, Sol Kim, Mikhail Krinitskiy, Juan M. Lora, Beth McClenny, Allison Michaelis, John P. O’Brien, Christina M. Patricola, Alexandre M. Ramos, Eric J. Shearer, Wen-Wen Tung, Paul A. Ullrich, Michael F. Wehner, Kevin Yang, Rudong Zhang, Zhenhai Zhang, and Yang Zhou. 2020. “Detection Uncertainty Matters for Understanding Atmospheric Rivers.” *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 101 (6): E790–96. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0348.1>.
- O’Brien, Travis Allen, Michael F. Wehner, Christine A. Shields, L. Ruby Leung, Bin Guan, Juan M. Lora, Elizabeth McClenny, Kyle M. Nardi, Alexandre M. Ramos, Ricardo Tomé, Chandan Sarangi, Eric J. Shearer, Paul A. Ullrich, Colin Zarzycki, Burlen Loring, and Swen Brands. 2021. “ARTMIP Tier 2 CMIP5/6 Catalogues.” Zenodo, December 10. <https://doi.org/10.26024/s4p7-pf13>.
- Park, Ju-Hee, Seok-Geun Oh, and Myoung-Seok Suh. 2013. “Impacts of Boundary Conditions on the Precipitation Simulation of RegCM4 in the CORDEX East Asia Domain.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 118 (4): 1652–67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50159>.
- Rush, W. D., J. M. Lora, C. B. Skinner, S. A. Menemenlis, C. A. Shields, P. Ullrich, T. A. O’Brien, S. Brands, B. Guan, K. S. Mattingly, E. McClenny, K. Nardi, A. Nellikkattil, A. M. Ramos, K. J. Reid, E. Shearer, R. Tomé, J. D. Wille, L. R. Leung, F. M. Ralph, J. J. Rutz, M. Wehner, Z. Zhang, M. Lu, and K. T. Quagrain. 2025. “Atmospheric River Detection Under Changing Seasonality and Mean-State Climate: ARTMIP Tier 2 Paleoclimate Experiments.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 130 (1): e2024JD042222. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JD042222>.
- Rutz, Jonathan J., Christine A. Shields, Juan M. Lora, Ashley E. Payne, Bin Guan, Paul Ullrich, Travis O’Brien, L. Ruby Leung, F. Martin Ralph, Michael Wehner, Swen Brands, Allison Collow, Naomi Goldenson, Irina Gorodetskaya, Helen Griffith, Karthik Kashinath, Brian Kawzenuk, Harinarayan Krishnan, Vitaliy Kurlin, David Lavers, Gudrun Magnusdottir, Kelly Mahoney, Elizabeth McClenny, Grzegorz Muszynski, Phu Dinh Nguyen, Mr. Prabhat, Yun Qian, Alexandre M. Ramos, Chandan Sarangi, Scott Sellars, T. Shulgina, Ricardo Tome, Duane Waliser, Daniel Walton, Gary Wick, Anna M. Wilson, and Maximiliano Viale. 2019. “The Atmospheric River Tracking Method Intercomparison Project (ARTMIP): Quantifying Uncertainties in Atmospheric River Climatology.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 124 (24): 13777–802. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD030936>.

- Saji, N. H., B. N. Goswami, P. N. Vinayachandran, and T. Yamagata. 1999. "A Dipole Mode in the Tropical Indian Ocean." *Nature* 401 (6751): 360–63. <https://doi.org/10.1038/43854>.
- San-Martín, D., R. Manzananas, S. Brands, S. Herrera, and J. M. Gutiérrez. 2017. "Reassessing Model Uncertainty for Regional Projections of Precipitation with an Ensemble of Statistical Downscaling Methods." *Journal of Climate* 30 (1): 203–23. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0366.1>.
- Scaife, Adam A., and Doug Smith. 2018. "A Signal-to-Noise Paradox in Climate Science." *Npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* 1 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-018-0038-4>.
- Seneviratne, Sonia I., and Mathias Hauser. 2020. "Regional Climate Sensitivity of Climate Extremes in CMIP6 Versus CMIP5 Multimodel Ensembles." *Earth's Future* 8 (9): e2019EF001474. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019EF001474>.
- Sobolowski, Stefan, Samuel Somot, Jesus Fernandez, Guillaume Evin, Swen Brands, Douglas Maraun, Sven Kotlarski, Martin Jury, Rasmus E. Benestad, Claas Teichmann, Ole B. Christensen, Katharina Bülow, Erasmo Buonomo, Eleni Katragkou, Christian Steger, Silje Sørland, Grigory Nikulin, Carol McSweeney, Andreas Dobler, Tamzin Palmer, Renate Wilcke, Julien Boé, Lukas Brunner, Aurélien Ribes, Said Qasmi, Pierre Nabat, Florence Sevault, and Thomas Oudar. 2025. "GCM Selection & Ensemble Design: Best Practices and Recommendations from the EURO-CORDEX Community." *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, May 26, BAMS-D-23-0189.1. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-23-0189.1>.
- Soden, Brian J., Richard T. Wetherald, Georgiy L. Stenchikov, and Alan Robock. 2002. "Global Cooling After the Eruption of Mount Pinatubo: A Test of Climate Feedback by Water Vapor." *Science* 296 (5568): 727–30. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.296.5568.727>.
- Swaminathan, Ranjini, Jacob Schewe, Jeremy Walton, Klaus Zimmermann, Colin Jones, Richard A. Betts, Chantelle Burton, Chris D. Jones, Matthias Mengel, Christopher P. O. Reyer, Andrew G. Turner, and Katja Weigel. 2024. "Regional Impacts Poorly Constrained by Climate Sensitivity." *Earth's Future* 12 (12): e2024EF004901. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024EF004901>.
- Tradowsky, Jordis S., Sjoukje Y. Philip, Frank Kreienkamp, Sarah F. Kew, Philip Lorenz, Julie Arrighi, Thomas Bettmann, Steven Caluwaerts, Steven C. Chan, Lesley De Cruz, Hylke de Vries, Norbert Demuth, Andrew Ferrone, Erich M. Fischer, Hayley J. Fowler, Klaus Goergen, Dorothy Heinrich, Yvonne Henrichs, Frank Kaspar, Geert Lenderink, Enno Nilson, Friederike E. L. Otto, Francesco Ragone, Sonia I. Seneviratne, Roop K. Singh, Amalie Skålevåg, Piet Termonia, Lisa Thalheimer, Maarten van Aalst, Joris Van den Bergh, Hans Van de Vyver, Stéphane Vannitsem, Geert Jan van Oldenborgh, Bert Van Schaeybroeck, Robert Vautard, Demi Vonk, and Niko Wanders. 2023. "Attribution of the Heavy Rainfall Events Leading to Severe Flooding in Western Europe during July 2021." *Climatic Change* 176 (7): 90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-023-03502-7>.
- Trenberth, Kevin E., Grant W. Branstator, David Karoly, Arun Kumar, Ngar-Cheung Lau, and Chester Ropelewski. 1998. "Progress during TOGA in Understanding and Modeling Global Teleconnections Associated with Tropical Sea Surface Temperatures." *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 103 (C7): 14291–324. <https://doi.org/10.1029/97JC01444>.

- Ummenhofer, Caroline C., Hyodae Seo, Young-Oh Kwon, Rhys Parfitt, Swen Brands, and Terrence M. Joyce. 2017. "Emerging European Winter Precipitation Pattern Linked to Atmospheric Circulation Changes over the North Atlantic Region in Recent Decades." *Geophysical Research Letters* 44 (16): 8557–66. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL074188>.
- Williamson, Mark S., Chad W. Thackeray, Peter M. Cox, Alex Hall, Chris Huntingford, and Femke J. M. M. Nijssen. 2021. "Emergent Constraints on Climate Sensitivities." *Reviews of Modern Physics* 93 (2): 025004. <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.93.025004>.
- Woollings, Tim, David Barriopedro, John Methven, Seok-Woo Son, Olivia Martius, Ben Harvey, Jana Sillmann, Anthony R. Lupo, and Sonia Seneviratne. 2018. "Blocking and Its Response to Climate Change." *Current Climate Change Reports* 4 (3): 287–300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-018-0108-z>.
- Xue, Yongkang, Zavisla Janjic, Jimmy Dudhia, Ratko Vasic, and Fernando De Sales. 2014. "A Review on Regional Dynamical Downscaling in Intraseasonal to Seasonal Simulation/Prediction and Major Factors That Affect Downscaling Ability."